

THE EFFECT OF FILAMENT-WINDING MOSAIC PATTERNS ON THE STRENGTH OF THIN-WALLED COMPOSITE SHELLS

E.V. Morozov

School of Mechanical Engineering, University of KwaZulu-Natal, Durban 4041, South Africa

SUMMARY: The paper deals with the modelling and stress analysis of filament-wound composite shells. Existing approaches to the structural analysis of composite shells are usually based on the implementation of mechanics of composite laminates. However, there are some manufacturing effects, specific for the filament winding process, which could significantly affect the stress and strain fields in the thin-walled composite shells. One of such effects is related to the filament-winding mosaic pattern of the composite layer and usually is not considered in the general stress analysis procedures, including existing finite element software packages. The paper presents results of the modelling and analysis of composite cylindrical shells with different types of filament-winding mosaic patterns. The differences in the numerically predicted stress values caused by the mosaic pattern effect are demonstrated using particular examples. As shown, the actual level of stresses in the thin-walled filament wound composite shells could be underestimated in some cases by the stress analysis based on the conventional mechanics of laminated structures.

KEYWORDS: composite shells, filament winding pattern, stress analysis, manufacturing effects

INTRODUCTION

Filament-wound composite shells of revolution are widely used in various applications, such as pipelines, pressure vessels, tanks for gases and liquids, rocket motor casings, etc. Modelling and stress analysis of such structural components is normally based on the implementation of mechanics of composite laminates [1]. Since the fibre orientation is the decisive factor in the strength of fibre-reinforced structures, the stress analysis is usually performed using the information concerning the number of layers, their stacking sequence and orientation, geometric and mechanical characteristics. According to this approach, composite material is considered as a system of layers with given properties. Correspondingly, composite shells of revolution fabricated by filament winding are usually modelled as laminated structures either composed from the orthotropic layers with symmetrical reinforcement: $\pm\phi_i$, or from the separate plies oriented under some angles $+\phi_i$ and $-\phi_i$ (i is the layer number) to the shell meridian. The former approach is based on the concept of the homogeneous $\pm\phi$ angle-ply orthotropic layer [1] and, as demonstrated in this paper, does not take into account some specific features of the filament wound structure. The latter way of modelling suits well to the analysis of laminated composite plates but it does not reflect the real structure of the conventional filament wound

shells either. Both aforementioned modelling approaches and methodologies are commonly accepted and implemented in the existent FEM software packages capable to handle mechanical analysis of laminated composite structures.

The real material structure of the composite $\pm\phi$ angle-ply filament wound layer is different from what the above mentioned models could offer. As a matter of fact, the filament wound layer is composed from the two plies with $+\phi$ and $-\phi$ orientation of fibres and these plies are interlaced in the process of filament winding. As a result, the structure of the layer is characterised by the distinctive regular mosaic pattern consisting of the triangular-shaped, repeating in chess-board fashion two-ply units with alternating $\pm\phi$ and $\mp\phi$ reinforcement. The units are arranged in regular geometric pattern around circumference and along the axis of rotation (Fig. 1) [1].

Fig. 1: Angle-ply layer of a filament wound shell

The sensitivity of composite cylinders to the filament-winding patterns was considered in [2-4]. As was shown, the mechanical response of the filament-wound structure was influenced by the elastic couplings and the scale of the repeating units around the circumference of the cylinder. In the current paper the results of the stress analysis of the composite cylindrical shells with different scales of mosaic filament-winding patterns are presented. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate how this structural feature of the filament wound layer, predetermined by the fabrication process, affects the strength characteristics of the thin-walled composite shells.

FILAMENT-WOUND SHELLS AND ANALYSIS OF LAMINATED STRUCTURES

Structure of the filament-wound $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers

Filament wound composite shells usually consist of the number of $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers wound in a helical pattern onto a mandrel. Each layer is a combination of two alternating plies with the angles of fibre orientation $+\phi$ and $-\phi$ to the shell meridian (Fig. 2) [1]. As previously discussed, these plies are interlaced in the filament winding process in such a way that the resulting angle-ply layer has a specific filament-winding mosaic pattern consisting of triangular-shaped repeating units around circumference and in the shell meridian direction (along the axis of rotation) (see Fig. 1). Each unit consists of two plies with either $[+\phi/-\phi]$ or $[-\phi/+\phi]$ structure and they are not interlaced within the unit area. If, for instance, some unit consists of the top

triangular-shaped ply, reinforced with fibres oriented under angle $+\phi$, and the bottom one reinforced with the angle $-\phi$, then the neighbouring adjacent units have an inverse structure: their top plies are reinforced under angle $-\phi$, and the bottom ones are reinforced under $+\phi$. These units are alternating in the hoop and meridian directions creating the mosaic pattern of the layer (see Fig. 1).

Fig. 2: Two $+\phi$ and $-\phi$ plies forming an angle-ply layer

The size of the unit and correspondingly the texture of the angle-ply layer could be controlled by the fabrication process parameters of the filament winding for one and the same angle of filament orientation ϕ [2].

The filament winding processes of the cylindrical shells with different winding mosaic patterns (numbers of the triangular-shaped units) are illustrated in Fig. 3(a). The numbered sequences of the fibre band placing order onto a mandrel are shown for the mandrel cross-sections in the cases of 2-, 4-, 8-, and 16-unit layer structures of the filament-wound cylindrical shells that have 2, 4, 8, and 16 triangular-shaped units around the circumference respectively.

Fig. 3: Schematic of the filament winding process (a) and filament wound shells with different mosaic patterns (b)

Black and white circles correspond to the cross-sections of the fibre bands placed one by one as numbered onto the mandrel surface in a spiral pattern around the mandrel at one and the same helix angle ϕ . Black and white colours denote the opposite directions of the fibre band placement carriage movements (back and forth moves) along the axis of the mandrel rotation. Continuation of the winding procedure finally completes a surface layer of two filament thicknesses on the mandrel. If necessary, the operation could be repeated to form additional layers until the desired part thickness has been obtained. The corresponding one-layered filament-wound composite cylindrical shells with 2-, 4-, 8-, and 16-unit layer structures are shown in Fig. 3(b).

Angle-ply layer modelling

As already noted, there are two main approaches to the modelling of the filament-wound $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers that are normally employed for the mechanical analysis of laminated shells composed from such layers. Both models are usually offered by the existing software packages and are widely used for the general stress analysis of composite plates and shells.

Homogeneous orthotropic $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layer

The first approach is based on the assumption that the filament-wound shells are usually composed from a large number of $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers. This is used as justification for the treatment of the $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layer as an orthotropic and homogeneous. Such layer is described by the following set of the constitutive equations [1]:

$$\begin{aligned}\sigma_x &= A_{11}\varepsilon_x + A_{12}\varepsilon_y, & \sigma_y &= A_{21}\varepsilon_x + A_{22}\varepsilon_y \\ \tau_{xy} &= A_{44}\gamma_{xy}, & \tau_{xz} &= A_{55}\gamma_{xz}, & \tau_{yz} &= A_{66}\gamma_{yz}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

The stiffness coefficients A_{mn} are specified as follows

$$\begin{aligned}A_{11} &= \bar{E}_1 c^4 + \bar{E}_2 s^4 + 2E_{12} c^2 s^2 \\ A_{12} &= A_{21} = \bar{E}_1 \nu_{12} + (\bar{E}_1 + \bar{E}_2 - 2E_{12}) c^2 s^2 \\ A_{22} &= \bar{E}_1 s^4 + \bar{E}_2 c^4 + 2E_{12} c^2 s^2 \\ A_{44} &= (\bar{E}_1 + \bar{E}_2 - 2\bar{E}_1 \nu_{12}) c^2 s^2 + G_{12} (c^2 - s^2)^2 \\ A_{55} &= G_{13} c^2 + G_{23} s^2 \\ A_{66} &= G_{13} s^2 + G_{23} c^2\end{aligned}\quad (2)$$

where

$$\bar{E}_{1,2} = \frac{E_{1,2}}{1 - \nu_{12}\nu_{21}}, \quad E_{12} = \bar{E}_1 \nu_{12} + 2G_{12}, \quad c = \cos\phi, \quad s = \sin\phi,$$

E_1 and E_2 are the longitudinal and transverse moduli, ν_{12} and ν_{21} are Poisson's ratios ($E_1\nu_{12} = E_2\nu_{21}$), and G_{12} , G_{13} and G_{23} are the shear moduli of the unidirectional ply.

Apparently, the thickness of the homogeneous orthotropic layer, h is equal to two thicknesses of the unidirectional ply, δ ($h = 2\delta$).

The laminates consisting of the layers with the same mechanical properties are homogeneous laminates, and for the orthotropic layers under consideration the constitutive equations that link stress resultants and couples with the corresponding generalized strains of the reference surface have the following form (the middle surface of the laminate is taken as the reference surface):

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_x &= B_{11}\varepsilon_x^0 + B_{12}\varepsilon_y^0 & N_y &= B_{21}\varepsilon_x^0 + B_{22}\varepsilon_y^0 & N_{xy} &= B_{44}\gamma_{xy}^0 \\
 M_x &= D_{11}\kappa_x + D_{12}\kappa_y & M_y &= D_{21}\kappa_x + D_{22}\kappa_y & M_{xy} &= D_{44}\kappa_{xy} \\
 V_x &= S_{55}\gamma_x & V_y &= S_{66}\gamma_y
 \end{aligned} \tag{3}$$

where the stress resultants and couples are specified as

$$\begin{aligned}
 N_x &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_x dz & N_y &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_y dz & N_{xy} &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \tau_{xy} dz \\
 M_x &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_x z dz & M_y &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \sigma_y z dz & M_{xy} &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \tau_{xy} z dz \\
 V_x &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \tau_{xz} dz & V_y &= \int_{-h/2}^{h/2} \tau_{yz} dz
 \end{aligned}$$

and the stiffness coefficients are calculated as follows:

$$B_{mn} = A_{mn} h \quad D_{mn} = A_{mn} \frac{h^3}{12} \quad S_{mn} = A_{mn} h$$

The generalized strains of the reference (middle) surface of the laminate correspond to the following basic deformations of the layer: in-plane tension or compression ($\varepsilon_x^0, \varepsilon_y^0$), in-plane shear (γ_{xy}^0), bending in xz - and yz -plane (κ_x, κ_y), twisting (κ_{xy}), and transversal shear (γ_x, γ_y).

Antisymmetric balanced $\pm \phi$ angle-ply layer

The second approach treats the angle-ply layer as an antisymmetric balanced laminate consisting of $+\phi$ and $-\phi$ unidirectional plies as shown in Fig. 4 [1].

Fig. 4: Unbonded view of an antisymmetric angle-ply layer

As shown, the angle-ply layer in this case consists of two plies with the same thickness $\delta = h/2$ and orientation angles $+\phi$ and $-\phi$. If the mating surface of the plies, which is the middle surface of the laminate, is selected as a reference surface, then the constitutive equations for this layer are

$$\begin{aligned}
N_x &= B_{11}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x^0 + B_{12}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y^0 + C_{14}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_{xy} \\
N_y &= B_{21}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x^0 + B_{22}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y^0 + C_{24}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_{xy} \\
N_{xy} &= B_{44}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{xy}^0 + C_{41}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_x + C_{42}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_y \\
M_x &= C_{14}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{xy}^0 + D_{11}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_x + D_{12}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_y \\
M_y &= C_{24}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_{xy}^0 + D_{21}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_x + D_{22}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_y \\
M_{xy} &= C_{41}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_x^0 + C_{42}\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_y^0 + D_{44}\boldsymbol{\kappa}_{xy} \\
V_x &= S_{55}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_x + S_{56}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_y \quad V_y = S_{65}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_x + S_{66}\boldsymbol{\gamma}_y
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

where the stiffness coefficients are calculated as follows:

$$B_{mn} = A_{mn}h \quad C_{mn} = -\frac{h^2}{4}A_{mn} \quad D_{mn} = \frac{h^3}{12}A_{mn} \quad (h = 2\delta) \tag{5}$$

The coefficients characterizing the transverse shear, S_{55} , S_{66} , and $S_{56} = S_{65}$ are calculated in terms of the stiffness coefficients A_{55} , A_{66} (see equations (2)) and $A_{56} = A_{65} = (G_{13} - G_{23})cs$ [1]. The set of stiffness coefficients (2) must be expanded and should include the following coefficients

$$\begin{aligned}
A_{14} &= A_{41} = [\bar{E}_1c^2 - \bar{E}_2s^2 - E_{12}(c^2 - s^2)]cs \\
A_{24} &= A_{42} = [\bar{E}_1s^2 - \bar{E}_2c^2 + E_{12}(c^2 - s^2)]cs
\end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

As can be seen, the layer is anisotropic because $+\phi$ and $-\phi$ plies are located in different planes with regard to the reference (middle) surface. According to (4), this type of the layer has stretching-twisting and bending-shear couplings. Homogeneous model of the layer (see Eqs. (3)) ignores this fact and yields $C_{14} = C_{24} = 0$.

Actual structure of the $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layer

Both considered above models do not reflect the real structure of the angle-ply layer determined by the specifics of the filament winding process detailed in previous Sections. The first approach replaces the real structure of the $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layer with the homogeneous orthotropic layer neglecting the filament-winding mosaic pattern and the anisotropy of the layer. Although, the second approach reflects the anisotropy of the angle-ply layer but at the same time it fails to take into account its real texture. According to this approach, the angle-ply layer is considered to be composed from two $+\phi$ and $-\phi$ plies with either the whole $+\phi$ ply placed on top of the $-\phi$ ply or vice versa without interlacing. This model works well for the laminated composite plates but does not take into account the fact that the real structure of the filament-wound layer is constructed from the alternating triangular-shaped areas as a result of interlacing of unidirectional plies.

As discussed above, the real filament-wound angle-ply layer is composed of triangular-shaped repeating units placed around circumference and along the axis of rotation in the chess-board fashion. Each unit consists of two plies with either $[+\phi/-\phi]$ or $[-\phi/+\phi]$ structure and these plies are not interlaced within the unit area. This means that Eqs. (4) are applicable to the separate units that belong to one or another alternating groups, i.e. the units with the $[+\phi/-\phi]$ and the units with the $[-\phi/+\phi]$ layer structure respectively. The differences between these two groups of the alternating units are in the coefficients A_{14} , A_{24} and A_{56} that are responsible for the anisotropic behavior of the two-ply layer. As a result, the units from these two groups exhibit antisymmetric opposite anisotropic stretching-twisting and bending-shear coupling effects alternating along the circumference and axis of rotation of the shell. Due to general alternating pattern of the units (chess-board structure) and their interactions within a layer the anisotropic effects are balancing each other inducing, at the same time, additional stresses in the layer. The model which takes into account this effect is developed and implemented in this work in conjunction with the finite element analysis in order to investigate the mechanical response of the filament-wound $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers with different filament-winding mosaic patterns.

FILAMENT-WINDING MOSAIC PATTERN, FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING AND STRESS ANALYSIS

In order to investigate the effect of the filament-winding mosaic pattern the stress analysis of the cylindrical shells with different layer structures was performed. The shells under consideration were composed of one filament-wound $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layer and loaded with internal pressure. The solid modelling (Solid Edge) and finite element analysis (MSC NASTRAN) techniques were employed to model the shells with different mosaic pattern structures. Each shell was partitioned into triangular-shaped units according to the particular filament-winding pattern (see Fig. 5). Correspondingly, the finite elements were also combined into the respective alternating groups. The composite material for the finite elements from each of these groups was defined as either $[+\phi/-\phi]$ or $[-\phi/+\phi]$ laminate. Using this approach, the stress analyses were performed for the shells with three different filament-winding patterns. The results were compared to those based on the concept of the homogeneous orthotropic angle-ply layer and obtained from the conventional finite element analysis and the analytical solution built upon the membrane theory of shells and equations (3).

The cylindrical shells under consideration were reinforced with the winding angle of $\phi = \pm 60^\circ$ and loaded with internal pressure of 1 MPa. Mechanical properties of the unidirectional glass-epoxy composite ply were taken as follows: $E_1 = 60$ GPa, $E_2 = 13$ GPa, $\nu_{21} = 0.3$, $G_{12} = 3.4$ GPa [1]. The ends of each shell were clamped and the distance between the ends (length of the cylinder) was fixed and equal to 140 mm. Diameter of the cylinder was 60 mm and total thickness of the wall was equal to 1.4 mm (with the thickness of the unidirectional ply $\delta = 0.7$ mm). Stress analyses have been performed for the four different types of the shells.

The first cylinder was modelled as a homogeneous orthotropic angle-ply layer and analysed using both, the analytical approach based on the application of the membrane shell theory and equations (3), and conventional FE analysis using the definitions of the composite material and finite element models available within MSC NASTRAN software.

The other three cylinders had 2, 4, and 8 triangular-shaped units around the circumference respectively, and were analysed using the FE modelling of the shells partitioned into mosaic patterns. The original and deformed shell models are shown in Fig. 5. As can be seen, the deformations developed in the shells distinctly reflect the corresponding filament-winding mosaic texture. The corresponding calculated values of stresses along and across fibres, σ_1 , σ_2 and shear stresses, τ_{12} acting in the plies are presented in Table 1.

Fig. 5: Original and deformed models

As follows from the data presented in the Table, the analytical solution and conventional FE analysis provide close values of the stresses in the plies (e.g. $\sigma_1 = 25.57$ MPa (analytical) and $\sigma_1 = 24.9$ MPa (FEA)). As for the 2-, 4-, and 8-unit cylinders, the distributions of stresses in these shells are substantially different. First of all, the stress distributions are not uniform along the cylinder length and around the circumference. The corresponding ranges of the stress values are shown in Table 1. Secondly, the predicted values of the maximum stresses acting along the fibres for the 2-unit shell are significantly higher compared to those obtained from the

conventional analysis (see Table 1), and reach the level of 40.99 MPa. It appears that with the increase of number of triangular mosaic units and corresponding reduction in the relative size of each unit (4-unit shell and 8-unit shell) the maximum values of stresses acting along the fibres are decreased (e.g., $\sigma_1 = 27.3$ MPa for 8-unit shell) closing to the value determined by the conventional analyses.

Table 1: Results of the stress analysis for the conventional and 2-, 4-, and 8-unit cylinders

Filament-winding patterns	σ_1 , MPa	σ_2 , MPa	τ_{21} , MPa
Conventional laminated cylinder, analytical solution	25.57	3.43	1.6
Conventional laminated cylinder, FEA	24.9	3.79	1.98
2-unit filament-wound cylinder	10.0 – 40.99	13.9 – 17.7	1.66 – 4.82
4-unit filament-wound cylinder	11.6 – 33.2	12.7 – 20.3	2.47 – 5.33
8-unit filament-wound cylinder	14.84 – 27.30	13.6 – 18.2	3.17 – 4.94

The similar effect has been observed for the physically tested thin-walled carbon-phenolic composite cylinders with different filament winding patterns [2]. The shells were tested under internal pressure with the measurements of the axial and circumferential strains performed during the test. The corresponding load-strain curves and failure modes are shown in Fig. 6. As can be seen, the failure loads for the 4- and 16- unit cylinders are substantially higher compared to the 2-unit shell. This is in agreement with the results of the numerical analysis according to which the shells with higher level of ply interlacing (4-, 8-unit shells) have a lower level of maximum stress σ_1 (see Table 1).

All this provides an indication that the level of stresses in the thin-walled filament wound composite shells could be underestimated in some cases by the general stress analysis based on the conventional mechanics of laminated structures, which does not take into account the filament-winding mosaic pattern of the $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers. This effect is most pronounced for the thin-walled shells. As for the multilayered laminated shells with the structure $[\pm\phi]_p$, where p is the number of $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers, the mosaic effect would manifest itself to the lesser extent. It has been shown in [1], that the stretching-twisting and bending-shear coupling coefficients for multilayered laminates are calculated as follows

$$C_{mn} = -\frac{1}{2} A_{mn} h \delta \quad (7)$$

where, h is the laminate thickness, δ the ply thickness, and A_{mn} are material stiffness coefficients specified by Eqs. (2). If the laminate is composed of large number of $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers and the

thickness of the single ply, δ is small compared to the overall thickness of the laminate, then the effect of the filament-winding pattern is not strong. Moreover, some calculations show that the coefficients (7) practically do not influence the behaviour of such laminate for $h/\delta \geq 20$ [1].

Fig.6: Experimental load-strain diagrams for composite shells with different mosaic patterns: (a) 2-unit cylinder; (b) 4-unit cylinder; (c) 16-unit cylinder; (d) failure modes; (p is the internal pressure, ε_α and ε_β are the longitudinal and hoop strains respectively)

The susceptibility of the multilayered thin-walled shell to this effect would also depend on the in-plane mutual position of the consecutive layers composing the laminate. If the successive layers are wound in such a way that the triangular units with the same structure, say $[\pm\phi]_p$ are placed one on top of the other, then the effect of the mosaic pattern could propagate through the overall thickness of the laminate and, correspondingly, could be transmitted to the whole shell.

The other way of composing the multilayered shell could involve the stacking of the units with the opposite reinforcement structure. In this case the triangular units with the antisymmetric, $[\pm\phi]$ and $[\mp\phi]$ ply orientation would alternate across the thickness of the shell creating a symmetric laminate: $[[\pm\phi],[\mp\phi]]_p$, where p is the number of the double angle-ply layers ($[\pm\phi],[\mp\phi]$). In this case, the stretching-twisting and bending-shear coupling effects would balance each other inducing, however, additional interlaminar stresses.

Both above mentioned cases represent the regular structures of the laminated composite material across the thickness of the laminate. In order to fabricate composite shells with this type of regularities in the wall structure, the filament winding process would require additional adjustments. Otherwise, the positions of the consecutive $\pm\phi$ angle-ply filament-wound layers could be shifted arbitrarily relative to each other in axial and circumferential directions during the winding process. In this case, the triangular-shaped units, being still placed regularly within the layer, will be located in irregular manner across the thickness of the laminate. This would smear out the filament-winding pattern effect and could create some uncertainty for the modelling and assessment of the stress state of the structure in those cases when the mosaic effect could not be neglected.

CONCLUSIONS

The analysis of the effect of filament-winding mosaic patterns on the mechanical characteristics of thin-walled composite cylindrical shells is presented in this paper. It was demonstrated that due to some specifics of the fabrication process the actual structure of the $\pm\phi$ angle-ply filament-wound layer is more complex compared to that commonly adopted as the basis for the angle-ply modelling usually employed to perform stress analysis of composite laminated structures.

It was found that the mechanical behaviour of thin-walled filament-wound composite shells is sensitive to the filament-winding patterns and the stress and strain distributions are affected by the size of the triangular mosaic units and their numbers per unit of length in both the longitudinal and circumferential (hoop) directions. The numerical results obtained from the finite element analyses show that there could be substantial differences in the stress values at the ply level calculated for the one-layered cylindrical filament-wound shells with different mosaic patterns. The stress distributions are not uniform along the length of the shell and its circumference and the maximum stresses acting along the fibres are higher than those calculated using conventional modeling techniques. This means that the values of the stresses acting in the thin-walled filament wound composite shells could be underestimated in some cases if the analysis does not take into account the particular filament-winding mosaic patterns of the $\pm\phi$ angle-ply layers.

REFERENCES

1. Vasiliev, V.V. and Morozov, E.V. *Mechanics and Analysis of Composite Materials*. Elsevier Science, 2001.
2. Vorobey, V.V., Morozov, E.V. and Tatarnikov, O.V. *Analysis of Thermostressed Composite Structures*. Moscow, Mashinostroenie, 1992 (in Russian).
3. Jensen, D.W. and Pai, S.P. "Theoretical sensitivity of composite cylinders in compression to filament-winding pattern", *Proc. 9th Int. Conf. on Composite Materials (ICCM-9), Madrid, 1993*, Vol. 3, pp. 447-454.
4. Morozov, E.V., Hoarau, M. and Morozov, K.E. "Filament-Winding Patterns and Stress Analysis of Thin-Walled Composite Cylinders". *Proc. Fiber Society 2003 Symposium*, June 30-July 2, 2003, Loughborough University, Loughborough, UK.